

PERSPECTIVES

Targeting plant cysteine oxidase activity for improved submergence tolerance

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SUMMARY

Plant cysteine oxidases (PCOs) are plant O₂-sensing enzymes. They catalyse the O₂-dependent step which initiates the proteasomal degradation of Group VII ethylene response transcription factors (ERF-VIIs) via the N-degron pathway. When submerged, plants experience a reduction in O₂ availability; PCO activity therefore decreases and the consequent ERF-VII stabilisation leads to upregulation of hypoxia-responsive genes which enable adaptation to low O₂ conditions. Resulting adaptations include entering an anaerobic quiescent state to maintain energy reserves and rapid growth to escape floodwater and allow O₂ transport to submerged tissues. Stabilisation of ERF-VIIs has been linked to improved survival post-submergence in *Arabidopsis*, rice (*Oryza sativa*) and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). Due to climate change and increasing flooding events, there is an interest in manipulating the PCO/ERF-VII interaction as a method of improving yields in flood-intolerant crops. An effective way of achieving this may be through PCO inhibition; however, complete ablation of PCO activity is detrimental to growth and phenotype, likely due to other PCO-mediated roles. Targeting PCOs will therefore require either temporary chemical inhibition or careful engineering of the enzyme structure to manipulate their O₂ sensitivity and/or substrate specificity. Sufficient PCO structural and functional information should make this possible, given the potential to engineer site-directed mutagenesis *in vivo* using CRISPR-mediated base editing. Here, we discuss the knowledge still required for rational manipulation of PCOs to achieve ERF-VII stabilisation without a yield penalty. We also take inspiration from the biocatalysis field to consider how enzyme engineering could be accelerated as a wider strategy to improve plant stress tolerance and productivity.

Keywords: plant cysteine oxidases, O₂ sensing, enzyme engineering, stress tolerance, submergence.

INTRODUCTION

Fundamental to all metabolic, catabolic and adaptive biological processes are enzymes. Enzymes are catalytic proteins that increase the rate of biochemical reactions by providing a stabilising scaffold for substrate binding and orientation. In so doing, enzymes reduce the energy needed for reaction progression and allow catalytic turnover rates, in some cases up to the limits of diffusion. Through diversity of structure and the use of co-factors, enzymes catalyse a diverse array of challenging reactions that support life. Enzymes have evolved such that their function meets a biological need, fine-tuning their activity for optimal survival and replication fitness of the organism.

In recent decades, plant survival has become more challenging due to rapidly changing environmental conditions. Plants are exposed to greater extremes of heat, ozone,

osmotic stress, salt, cold, low oxygen (hypoxia) and pest-derived toxins. Coupled with this there is a need for plants (crops) to be more productive and assimilate nitrogen and phosphorus more efficiently. Compared with the pace of change required, plant enzymes cannot evolve quickly enough to enable the plant to meet these needs (Wurtzel et al., 2019). Engineering enzymes involved in stress response or productivity pathways has the potential to allow their evolution to 'catch up' with the restrictions imposed on the plant, such that enzyme activity can be aligned to new environmental conditions or new requirements imposed by human activity.

Enzyme engineering (altering the properties of an enzyme by mutating individual or groups of amino acids) has been successfully utilised for decades to induce non-endogenous properties and is a common strategy used by

enzymologists seeking to understand structure/function relationships of isolated enzymes. Similar engineering strategies to manipulate enzyme function could be used to generate plant enzymes whose altered activity results in improved plant stress responses or increased productivity. Plant cysteine oxidases (PCOs) are O_2 -sensing enzymes that signal for the hypoxic conditions experienced upon submergence to trigger an adaptive response for plants to survive this stress. Here, we propose that PCOs are good candidates for targeted enzyme engineering. By manipulating their activity, either through small molecule inhibition or through targeted modulation of their structure and catalytic properties, it is possible that flood adaptive strategies could be prolonged to improve recovery in flood-susceptible crops.

THE ROLE OF PLANT CYSTEINE OXIDASES IN FLOOD ADAPTIVE STRATEGIES

All aerobic organisms need O_2 to survive. O_2 is the terminal electron acceptor in oxidative phosphorylation, enabling efficient ATP generation coupled to glucose consumption. Furthermore, O_2 is an important substrate in the production of a range of important biomolecules. If insufficient O_2 is available there is both a reduction in ATP production resulting in an energy crisis and potential for increased mitochondrial reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation, with potential for cell damage and death. Mechanisms have been identified in plants and animals which allow them to sense a reduction in O_2 availability (hypoxia) and adapt to this by initiating pathways which reduce demand for O_2 and/or increase O_2 supply (Hammarlund et al., 2020; Holdsworth and Gibbs, 2020).

In plants, acute hypoxia occurs upon flood-induced submergence, due to a reduced ability of O_2 to diffuse through

water compared to air (Bailey-Serres et al., 2012; Holdsworth and Gibbs, 2020). Adaptive physiological traits include 'escape' strategies triggered by ethylene accumulation, such as elongation of petioles and root aeration via aerenchyma formation (Loreti et al., 2016; Voesenek and Bailey-Serres, 2015), and energy-saving 'quiescence', whereby a metabolic switch to starch catabolism and anaerobic metabolism maintains sufficient ATP production for survival while growth is arrested (Bailey-Serres et al., 2012). These physiological adaptations are driven by transcription factors from the Group VII Ethylene Response Factor (ERF-VII) family. ERF-VIIs are conserved in all flowering plants, with five ERF-VIIs in Arabidopsis (HYPOXIA RESPONSE ELEMENT 1 [HRE1], HRE2, RELATED TO AP2.2 [RAP2.2], RAP2.12 and RAP2.3), each with a conserved N-terminal motif (N-MCGGAI/L). HRE1 and HRE2 are induced by hypoxia, whereas RAP2.2, RAP2.12 and RAP2.3 are constitutively expressed (Licausi et al., 2010). Under non-stress conditions, RAP2.12 is tethered to the cell membrane; during hypoxia, RAP2.12 release is triggered by decreased ATP availability (Licausi et al., 2011; Schmidt et al., 2018). This enables RAP2.12 translocation to the nucleus and upregulation of expression of a core set of 49 hypoxic response genes, many of which are involved in anaerobic metabolism (Lee et al., 2011; Mustroph et al., 2009).

Following co-translational methionine cleavage at ERF-VII N-termini, an N-terminal Cys (Nt-Cys) residue is exposed. This leaves the ERF-VIIs susceptible to degradation via the Arg/Cys branch of the N-degron proteolysis pathway (Figure 1) (Gibbs et al., 2011; Licausi et al., 2011; Varshavsky, 2019). When the Nt-Cys residue is oxidised, it becomes a substrate for arginylation by arginyl transferase (ATE1 and ATE2). Addition of an N-terminal Arg residue then renders ERF-VIIs targets for the ubiquitin

Figure 1. PCO-mediated regulation of the stability of ERF-VII transcription factors via the N-degron pathway. At normal O_2 concentrations (top), PCO enzymes catalyse oxidation of ERF-VII N-terminal cysteine residues to cysteine-sulphinic acid; subsequent ATE-catalysed arginylation renders the ERF-VIIs substrates for ubiquitin ligase PRT6, resulting in proteasomal degradation. In hypoxia (bottom), e.g. upon submergence, insufficient O_2 prevents PCO activity, rendering ERF-VIIs stable to initiate expression of genes which help adapt to the hypoxic conditions. PCO, plant cysteine oxidase (PDB ID: 6S7E; White et al., 2020); ATE, arginyl transferase; PRT6 (PDB ID: 6LHN; Kim et al., 2020); Ub, ubiquitin.

ligase PRT6 and proteasomal degradation. Nt-Cys oxidation is catalysed by the PCOs, which directly utilise O₂ as a co-substrate (Weits et al., 2014; White et al., 2017). Under normal O₂ levels, the ERF-VIIs are largely degraded by this Arg/Cys N-degron pathway. In hypoxic conditions, PCO activity is inefficient and ERF-VIIs are stabilised to initiate an adaptive response (Gibbs et al., 2011; Licausi et al., 2011). These enzymes therefore connect the availability of O₂ in the environment with the stability of the ERF-VIIs and the consequent hypoxic response.

The adaptive response to hypoxia in plants via PCO-catalysed ERF-VII oxidation is very similar to the adaptive response to hypoxia in animals, initiated by (a reduction in) enzyme-catalysed hydroxylation of prolyl residues in Hypoxia-Inducible Factor (HIF). Prolyl hydroxylases have been well characterised as O₂ sensors in humans (Ehrismann et al., 2007; Myllyharju, 2013; Tarhonskaya et al., 2014), which raised the possibility that the PCOs could perform a similar O₂-sensing role in plants. To act as O₂ sensors, the rate of PCO activity must be dependent on the O₂ concentration over a range that is physiologically relevant. This means that there will be a concentration-dependent response to decreasing O₂ availability, rather than sustained catalysis at low O₂ levels. The O₂ sensitivity of an enzyme can be characterised by kinetic constants, $K_M O_2$ values, which represent the affinity of an enzyme for O₂ and are indicative of its potential to elicit a concentration-dependent response to changes in O₂ availability. Kinetic investigation of the five PCOs from Arabidopsis revealed that their $K_M O_2$ values ranged from 5.45% (4.83 kPa) in AtPCO5 to 17.3% (16.5 kPa) in AtPCO4 (White et al., 2018). Meanwhile, O₂ concentrations in plant tissue range from near atmospheric in surface tissues to 7% in vascular tissues, down to 3–6% in regions of high metabolic activity, such as shoot apical meristems, and <1% in galls and in seed embryos (Van Dongen and Licausi, 2015; Weits et al., 2021). Thus, the $K_M O_2$ values of the AtPCOs, albeit obtained under non-physiological conditions, suggest that the activity of these enzymes is likely to be sensitive to physiologically relevant O₂ gradients, and they could act as plant O₂ sensors.

As O₂ sensors, PCO activity can act as a signalling response to changes in O₂ availability. This means that as plants become submerged and O₂ levels start to decrease, PCO activity will drop, resulting in increased stabilisation of ERF-VIIs. This, in combination with the accumulation of ethylene and increased ERF-VII production, enables the transcription of genes which allow adaptation to the low O₂ conditions before an energy crisis is reached. Those PCOs with high $K_M O_2$ values are the most sensitive and will be the first to reduce their activity in response to decreasing O₂. In Arabidopsis, this will likely be AtPCO4 and AtPCO1 ($K_M O_2$ values of 17.3 and 15.7%, respectively (White et al., 2018)). However, it would seem that ‘turning

off’ the hypoxic response is also important for plant recovery and fitness (Licausi et al., 2011). With lower $K_M O_2$ values of 7.37 and 5.35%, respectively (White et al., 2018), AtPCO2 and AtPCO5 would likely play an important role in destabilising the ERF-VIIs upon return to oxygenation. While AtPCO4 appears to be the most catalytically active enzyme towards RAP2.12/RAP2.2, kinetic parameters towards all substrates, including with respect to O₂, need to be determined in order to establish the dynamics of ERF-VII regulation in response to fluctuating O₂ levels.

INCREASING STRESS TOLERANCE THROUGH PCO MANIPULATION AND ERF-VII STABILISATION

There is evidence from a range of studies that stabilisation and/or increased levels of ERF-VII transcription factors can improve submergence survival. In Arabidopsis, overexpression of the AtERF-VII RAP2.2 (Hinz et al., 2010) and of the stable AtERF-VIIs HRE1 and HRE2 (with Nt-Cys replaced with Ala) (Gibbs et al., 2011) led to improved anoxia tolerance in seeds and seedlings. Upregulation of AtERF-VII RAP2.12 in 5-week-old plants improved submergence tolerance while aerobically grown plants retained normal growth characteristics (Licausi et al., 2011). In contrast, a constitutively stable RAP2.12 (where Nt-Cys was ‘hidden’ or removed) resulted in poorer aerobic growth and recovery from submergence (Licausi et al., 2011). In barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), inactivation of *PRT6* (which encodes the ubiquitin ligase component of the N-degron pathway) using RNA interference or mutation (via Targeting-Induced Local Lesions IN Genomes [TILLING]) increased hypoxic gene expression and improved recovery after 20 days waterlogging (Mendondo et al., 2016). Rice (*Oryza sativa*) plants with the ERF-VII SUB1A-1-encoding gene have extended submergence tolerance characteristics, enabling survival of complete submergence for 2 weeks or longer (Xu et al., 2006). Transfer of this gene into elite breeding lines has resulted in a 45% increase in yield relative to those without *SUB1A-1* after exposure to flooding (and a minimal effect on yield under non-flood conditions) (Dar et al., 2013). *SUB1A-1* does not seem to be regulated by the N-degron pathway (Gibbs et al., 2011) and therefore it is inherently stable. This is likely due to the *SUB1A-1* N-terminus being unavailable for modification due to interaction with its own C-terminus (Lin et al., 2019). *SUB1A-1* facilitates tolerance of a range of stresses, one of which is low O₂ via upregulation of two other rice Nt-Cys initiating ERF-VIIs (OsERFs 66 and 67). When these OsERFs were independently overexpressed, or when overexpressed by elevated *SUB1A-1*, improved submergence tolerance in submergence-sensitive rice cultivars was observed (Lin et al., 2019).

Collectively, these studies indicate that elevated ERF-VII levels have a beneficial effect with respect to submergence (and potentially desubmergence; Fukao et al., 2011) tolerance, but that constitutive overexpression, at least in

some circumstances, may be detrimental (Licausi et al., 2011). Elevation of ERF-VII levels, as opposed to complete stabilisation, could therefore be a promising strategy to improve flood tolerance in crops. As PCOs regulate levels of ERF-VIIs, altering the rate of activity of these enzymes is a viable route to achieve this. Total inhibition of PCO activity is not desirable, as this would have the same effect as complete ERF-VII stabilisation, as well as potential non-ERF-VII-related effects (see below). However, PCO activity could be altered in a condition-dependent manner, such as decreasing its rate with respect to O₂ or its rate of activity towards a certain substrate. With sufficient structural and mechanistic insight into enzyme function, the rate of activity of an enzyme can be 'artificially' manipulated, including in response to individual substrates. For example, the K_M O₂ of the human O₂-sensing enzyme prolyl hydroxylase 2 (PHD2) has been approximately halved via an active site mutation whilst its sensitivity to its primary substrate remained unchanged (Tarhonskaya et al., 2014). If the same is achieved for the PCOs, this could have the effect of prolonged ERF-VII stabilisation over the course of the submergence/desubmergence cycle. In contrast to up- or downregulation of the genes which express PCOs, which would lead to absolute and consistent changes in PCO activity, manipulating the O₂ sensitivity of the PCOs offers the opportunity to control their activity in an O₂ concentration-dependent manner: PCO activity in normoxia is therefore retained while ERF-VII stabilisation is sustained over a broader range of hypoxia.

As well as direct links between ERF-VII stabilisation and submergence tolerance, there is also evidence that ERF-VIIs are implicated in a wider range of stress responses (Gibbs et al., 2015). For example, Arabidopsis ERF-VII HRE2 is linked to improved osmotic stress tolerance (Park et al., 2011). RAP2.2, RAP2.12 and RAP2.3 have been shown to regulate responses to submergence-related oxidative and osmotic stresses via prolonged ABA-responsiveness (Papdi et al., 2015). In rice, SUB1A enhances tolerance to drought including dehydration stress following flooding, again including via enhanced ABA responsiveness (Fukao et al., 2011). In Arabidopsis and barley, stabilisation of ERF-VIIs through knockout or knockdown of *PRT6* also enhanced tolerance to high salt, high temperature, drought and oxidative stress (Vicente et al., 2017). Upregulation of RAP2.12 in Arabidopsis increased tolerance to high light, heat, aluminium and drought stress, likely through upregulation of apoplastic RbohD and ROS-induced stress signalling (Yao et al., 2017). Condition-dependent stabilisation of ERF-VIIs through PCO modulation could therefore have multiple beneficial effects in terms of stress resistance, particularly with respect to the compound stresses experienced upon submergence and desubmergence.

HOW TO ACHIEVE PCO MANIPULATION

In order to rationally modify the activity of the PCOs towards particular substrates, including O₂, structural and mechanistic knowledge is required. We and others have published structures of AtPCOs 2, 4 and 5 (Chen et al., 2021; White et al., 2020). These have revealed that the enzymes comprise a structure typical of Fe(II)-dependent dioxygenases with a double-stranded beta helix core, flanked by alpha helices, supporting an active site Fe(II) that is coordinated by three histidine residues. Comparison with small molecule thiol dioxygenases (e.g. cysteine dioxygenases (Gunawardana et al., 2021)) shows a high degree of conservation in terms of overall structure. The AtPCOs, however, have unique aspects that suggest tailored structural adaptation to oxidation of protein substrates and (potentially) O₂ sensing (Gunawardana et al., 2021). These include an 'open' entrance to the active site Fe(II) for protein substrate access and a variable loop region near the entrance to the active site which might be involved in substrate binding (White et al., 2020). AtPCO active site residues were also different from those of small molecule thiol dioxygenases, suggesting they might play unique roles in ERF-VII binding and oxidation.

We and others have generated variants of some of these active site residues, which revealed important roles for an Fe-binding histidine residue (AtPCO4 His164), a negatively charged aspartate close to the presumed Nt-Cys binding position (AtPCO4 Asp176) and a tyrosine residue whose OH group is directed towards the Fe binding site (AtPCO4 Tyr182) which might also play a role in correct substrate orientation in the active site (Chen et al., 2021; White et al., 2020). When these were substituted conservatively (His164Asp, Asp176Asn and Tyr182Phe), reductions in the rates of RAP2.12 oxidation were observed which were particularly marked for the His164Asp and Asp176Asn variants. Exploitation of a *pco1pco2pco4pco5* Arabidopsis model (Masson et al., 2019), which has stunted growth characteristics and elevated hypoxic gene expression, allowed determination of the effect of introducing specific AtPCO4 sequences. Reintroduction of wild-type AtPCO4 reconstituted a wild-type phenotype and reduced hypoxic gene expression. However, introduction of the His164Asp or Asp176Asn variants did not restore the wild-type phenotype, suggesting the inactivating effect seen for these variants using recombinant protein was maintained *in planta* (White et al., 2020). No apparent phenotypic improvement was observed for the His164Asp variant *in planta*, which was completely inactive *in vitro*. Interestingly, a restoration of female fertility was observed with the Asp176Asn variant, which had showed slight activity *in vitro*. Although the mechanism underlying this subtle phenotypic difference is unclear, it suggests differentiation between low and zero activity for the PCO enzymes at a biological level.

While these variants did not significantly improve the phenotypic characteristics of the *pco1pco2pco4pco5* Arabidopsis plants into which they were transformed, these experiments nevertheless demonstrated that the effects of AtPCO variants could be correlated between protein and plant. This provides a platform for testing future variants which are more specifically engineered to result in altered O₂ sensing or substrate selectivity characteristics (Figure 2). Those which engender improved submergence tolerance characteristics could then be introduced at the genome level via CRISPR/Cas-inspired base editing techniques (Huang and Puchta, 2021). However, PCO-catalysed ERF-VII oxidation and its impact on ERF-VII stability is not an isolated signalling pathway. There are of course other factors which may influence or be

influenced by manipulation of PCO function. To avoid PCO manipulation strategies which negatively impact plant growth, crop yield or other phenotypic characteristics, the full extent of biologically relevant PCO activities should be understood, as well as any competing factors which might influence PCO activity or ERF-VII stability. Further information is therefore needed on the role of PCOs in regulating the stability of non-ERF-VII substrates, as well as on how ROS and/or nitric oxide (NO) might impact ERF-VII Nt-Cys oxidation status.

Targeting PCO manipulation strategies towards specific substrates

The ERF-VIIs are defined by a sequence initiating motif (N-MCGGAI/L), with PCO-catalysed oxidation specifically

Figure 2. Enzyme engineering strategy to manipulate PCO activity. (1) Structure-guided mutagenesis generates variants of interest (AtPCO4 structure shown, PDB ID: 6S7E; White *et al.*, 2020). (2) Variants are tested in biochemical kinetic assays for O₂-sensing and substrate selectivity characteristics. (3) Variants of interest are introduced into a *pco1pco2pco4pco5* Arabidopsis model, under control of its endogenous promoter (White *et al.*, 2020), to test for growth and stress tolerance characteristics as well as substrate stability (to correlate with PCO activity). (4) Successful variants are genomically introduced via CRISPR base editing into Arabidopsis and phenotypic characterisation is repeated. (5) Variants inducing improved submergence tolerance characteristics in Arabidopsis are translated into crop species following biochemical validation of homologous characteristics.

targeting the Nt-Cys exposed by methionine cleavage. Meanwhile, there are >200 MetCys initiating sequences in Arabidopsis, all of which have the potential to be substrates for the PCOs. It is also known that the PCOs catalyse the oxidation of non-ERF-VII substrates. Vernalisation 2 (VRN2), a component of the polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) which regulates epigenetic gene repression, is a substrate of the PCOs (Gibbs et al., 2018). The stability of the transcription factor Little Zipper 2 (ZPR2) is also regulated by PCOs, such that accumulation of ZPR2 in the metabolically active hypoxic niche of shoot apical meristems is a driver of development (Weits et al., 2019). Other O₂-sensitive responses are also reported to be mediated by non-ERF-VII-related processes (Holdsworth, 2017) and Arabidopsis mutants lacking all five ERF-VIIs are viable and can display hypoxia-dependent behaviour (Abbas et al., 2015; Eysholdt-Derzso and Sauter, 2017; Giuntoli et al., 2017). Furthermore, the *pco1pco2pco4pco5* Arabidopsis model, as described above, shows severe phenotypic defects (Masson et al., 2019; White et al., 2020), indicating an important developmental role for PCO-mediated O₂ signalling. These findings directly and indirectly indicate that PCOs target Nt-Cys initiating proteins other than the ERF-VIIs.

Any strategy that manipulates PCO activity for increased ERF-VII stability may therefore concurrently impact PCO activity towards non-ERF-VII substrates. This could have negative impacts on development, growth and yield. Therefore, it is important to consider ways to engineer PCO activity towards (or away from) specific substrates. This is best achieved with a complete knowledge of target proteins; for PCOs it will therefore be important to explore further potential PCO-catalysed oxidation of Nt-Cys initiating proteins. Also important is a structural understanding of how the PCOs interact with their substrates, which will reveal how the PCO:substrate interface might be modified to engineer substrate selectivity (e.g. via reduced binding of ERF-VIIs whilst maintaining interactions with other substrates; Figure 2). Finally, it is necessary to understand the kinetics of PCO activity towards different substrates, particularly at different O₂ concentrations. It is interesting to note, for example, that, with the exception of AtPCO3, rates of AtPCO activity towards the peptide substrate representing VRN2 were much lower than towards the peptide substrate representing ERF-VII RAP2.12 (Gibbs et al., 2018). Understanding the dynamics of different PCO substrate regulation across O₂ gradients will direct engineering strategies for optimal outcomes, which may also include targeting specific PCO enzymes within one plant species. While improved submergence tolerance would be one successful outcome of a directed engineering strategy, the knowledge gained might also enable manipulation of PCO activity to impact other hypoxia-relevant processes, e.g.

development and tuber formation (Van Dongen and Licausi, 2015; Weits et al., 2021).

How does NO interface with PCO function?

As well as O₂, Arabidopsis ERF-VII levels are affected by NO (Gibbs et al., 2014). NO is an important signalling molecule in plants, involved in a number of developmental processes, so ERF-VII regulation could be an NO signalling integration point. It has been reported that the presence of both NO and O₂ are necessary for degradation of ERF-VIIs via the Arg/Cys-branch of the N-degron pathway and that ERF-VIIs are stabilised by the limited availability of either gas (Gibbs et al., 2011, 2014). Interestingly, ethylene pre-treatment of aerobic Arabidopsis plants has been reported to result in upregulation of an NO scavenger, phytohemoglobin 1 (PGB1); subsequent NO depletion stabilised ERF-VIIs and enabled acclimation to hypoxia (Hartman et al., 2019).

A similar observation has been made for N-degron pathway-mediated control of levels of human Regulator of G-protein Signalling (RGS) proteins involved in cardiovascular development (Hu et al., 2005). The non-enzymatic nitrosylation of the Nt-Cys of RGS4 promoted oxidation to form Cys-sulphonic acid, which then served as a substrate for subsequent arginylation and degradation (Hu et al., 2005). RGS4/5 Nt-Cys oxidation to Cys-sulphonic acid has subsequently been shown to be catalysed by O₂-dependent cysteamine dioxygenase (ADO), a PCO homologue found in humans (Masson et al., 2019). Although NO is not required for PCO-catalysed Cys-sulphonic acid formation and subsequent arginylation, a similar non-enzymatic NO- and O₂-mediated formation of Cys-sulphonic acid at ERF-VII N-termini could potentially take place in a process that is competitive with PCO function. Both Cys-sulphonic acid and Cys-sulphonic acid are substrates for arginyl transferases (although the kinetic efficiency of these substrates has not been compared; White et al., 2017). However, this does not account for the observation that absence of NO leads to ERF-VII accumulation, suggesting an indirect and as-yet unknown role for NO in promoting ERF-VII destabilisation. Overall, at the mechanistic level, the role of NO in ERF-VII destabilisation remains unclear. When designing PCO engineering strategies, consideration must be given as to whether NO-mediated ERF-VII destabilisation is a process that is competitive with PCO-catalysed ERF-VII oxidation (thus determining conditions under which PCO manipulation will be successful), or indeed whether NO amplifies or inhibits PCO activity.

Is ROS oxidation of Nt-Cys competitive with PCO activity?

ROS have important roles to play in signalling plant stress responses, and ROS levels are typically elevated in response to abiotic (and biotic) stresses, including hypoxia (Pucciariello and Perata, 2021; Sachdev et al., 2021;

Sasidharan et al., 2021). Counter-intuitively, ROS levels increase in hypoxia: O₂ is required as the terminal electron acceptor in oxidative phosphorylation so hypoxia or anoxia can lead to a greater likelihood of electron 'leakage' from the mitochondrial membrane resulting in ROS formation. Furthermore, O₂ fluctuations (e.g. recovery after submergence) can result in damaging ROS bursts (Yeung et al., 2019). In Arabidopsis, ERF-VIIs have been shown to upregulate production of RESPIRATORY BURST OXIDASE HOMOLOG D (RbohD), which produces a ROS burst but also triggers subsequent ROS scavenging processes; this is important in stress tolerance (Yao et al., 2017).

ROS are capable of cysteine oxidation in biological environments (Lo Conte et al., 2015), causing the reversible modification Cys-sulphenic acid, before further ROS-mediated oxidation to Cys-sulphinic and the irreversible conversion to Cys-sulphonic acid. It is therefore possible that ERF-VII Nt-Cys residues could become oxidised non-enzymatically in hypoxic conditions. Whether this is likely to occur depends very much on the proximity and local access of ROS molecules to ERF-VII N-termini, but H₂O₂ in particular is relatively long-lived and can diffuse through the cell (Akter et al., 2021). In contrast, ROS could inhibit PCO activity, in particular via oxidation of their active site Fe(II) ions; in this way ROS would contribute to stabilisation of ERF-VII and other substrates. It will be important to establish how ROS and O₂ interface to impact PCO activity and substrate stability.

ACCELERATING ENZYME ENGINEERING – LEARNING FROM THE BIOCATALYSIS FIELD

Due to the various interwoven signalling processes, several different factors will have to be considered in order to efficiently and selectively engineer changes in PCO O₂ sensitivity or substrate selectivity. Careful structural and functional analyses can identify the ideal target sites for PCO mutagenesis. For example, kinetic studies can help identify the substrates that are competitive with ERF-VII for PCO binding and crystal structures of PCOs complexed with these primary targets would reveal interaction surfaces that can be manipulated to favour one substrate over another. It will be necessary to couple these biochemical studies with those *in planta* to understand substrate location and the biological relevance of different PCO reactions.

All this information gathering will take time, yet it is not necessary to wait for all this information to start engineering PCO enzymes and trialling their effect *in vitro* and *in planta*. Indeed, a try-it-and-see approach in itself, driven by hypotheses such as potential O₂-binding residues in the active site or substrate-binding residues in local regions, will reveal useful mechanistic information that can support the knowledge platform for future engineering efforts. Given the pace of change in extreme global weather patterns and the urgent need for crops with improved stress

tolerance, there is a strong argument for a dual approach, to expedite the generation of optimised PCO enzymes.

At the same time, inspiration can be taken from the biocatalysis field in how to rapidly optimise enzyme function for a desired purpose. Biocatalysis is a growing area of research and application which complements synthetic organic chemistry. Enzymes are sourced and developed to catalyse a diverse array of reactions important in the commercial production of pharmaceuticals, fine chemicals, fragrances and flavours (Bell et al., 2021). Using biological catalysts (enzymes) is advantageous both because they can catalyse synthetically 'difficult' reactions efficiently and with stereochemical precision and because they can achieve this under 'greener' conditions than synthetic processes which are often energy-intensive, produce much waste and require rare metal catalysts (Pyser et al., 2021). Where once biocatalysis was opportunistic, taking advantage of naturally occurring enzymes, the field is now much more directive, using natural enzymes as scaffolds upon which to apply modifications in order to achieve a desired catalytic outcome. This can mean improving productivity, reaction conditions and substrate selectivity. Enzyme modification commonly combines directed evolution (iterative rounds of random mutagenesis and testing) with structural knowledge to generate a library of enzyme variants with modifications at strategic functional regions. Libraries are screened to identify new forms of the enzyme with optimal catalytic properties, which are improved on even further by additional rounds of modification. This type of approach has proved very successful in improving substrate selectivity and stereoselectivity in enzymatic product formation, highly relevant for the pharmaceutical industry (Li et al., 2018). It is conceivable that, given an appropriate screening platform, a similar approach could be adopted to generate novel PCO enzyme variants with optimal catalytic properties. Semi-rational directed evolution of target regions of the enzymes (i.e. those regions known to have a role in catalysis or substrate binding) could rapidly identify mutations which, when implemented *in planta*, demonstrate improved submergence tolerance characteristics.

The same principle of enzyme engineering could also be applied to other plant enzymes as part of wider efforts to improve crop productivity and stress tolerance. Significant efforts have been undertaken to improve the efficiency and productivity of the CO₂-capturing enzyme RuBisCO (Carmo-Silva et al., 2015). While progress has been limited, this is arguably because of the complexity and inherent inefficiencies of the enzyme. CO₂ and O₂ compete for RuBisCO binding and catalysis, with redundant RuBisCO/O₂ products requiring catabolism. There are also challenges in chloroplastic transformation to implement and test modified versions of the enzyme. 'Simpler' enzymes such as the PCOs may be more straightforward templates for engineering. As well as the PCOs, candidates could

include gibberellin oxidase enzymes, reduced activity of which, if in selected tissues, could result in the productive phenotype seen in semi-dwarf varieties of rice and barley (*Hordicum vulgare*) where genes encoding gibberellin biosynthesis enzymes are mutated (Sasaki et al., 2002). In combination with platforms which allow rapid analysis of enzyme function (e.g. recently reported micro-fluidic kinetic analysis Markin et al., 2021), as well as advances in gene editing technologies, there is considerable scope for enzyme engineering to play a major role in generating crops with improved stress resilience or productivity profiles.

TEMPORARY INHIBITION OF PCO ACTIVITY TO PRIME FOR SUBMERGENCE TOLERANCE

An enzyme engineering approach to modify PCO activity, when implemented genetically, will by its nature result in a permanent, heritable modification to the endogenous function of these O₂-sensing enzymes. While extensive efforts will be made during the design of such engineered enzymes to avoid detrimental side effects arising as a consequence of PCO engineering, there may of course be unavoidable phenotypic or metabolic alterations that are detrimental under normal or stress conditions.

An alternative approach to manipulate the activity of the PCOs is therefore via the 'classic' route of enzyme inhibition, i.e. developing small molecules that bind competitively or non-competitively to the active site to prevent substrate binding and/or oxidation. Typically, such molecules will mimic the size and shape of the substrate itself, so analogues of cysteine may be suitable candidates. Endogenous protein-based PCO substrates are likely to have a much greater number of interactions with the enzyme than a small molecule, however, so potency and the ability to achieve an intracellular concentration of inhibitor that is high enough to achieve a competitive inhibitory effect may be challenging. Peptidomimetic inhibitors may be more suitable mimics of endogenous substrates, but the increased size will present challenges for cell permeability. It may be that Fe(II)-chelating molecules, as applied to other plant Fe-dependent dioxygenases (Harrison et al., 2015), hold more promise as potential PCO inhibitors.

It might be challenging to imagine a scenario where an agrochemical format PCO inhibitor could be practically applied to submerged plants to prolong the stabilisation of ERF-VIIs and improve plant survival rates. However, the discovery that ethylene pre-treatment of plants results in improved submergence tolerance (via PGB1-mediated NO depletion and subsequent ERF-VII accumulation; Hartman et al., 2019) suggests that pre-treatment of plants with PCO inhibitors could have the same outcome. Agrochemical-induced ERF-VII stabilisation prior to the actual onset of submergence-induced hypoxia could therefore have a beneficial effect on subsequent survival outcomes.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Work is ongoing to manipulate the activity of the PCOs in order to stabilise ERF-VIIs and increase submergence tolerance in plants. Rational, structure-guided design and testing of PCO variants *in vitro* is followed by implementation of variants of interest into *in vivo* models (White et al., 2020). Iterative feedback at each stage of this working model allows refinement of successful variants (Figure 2), in particular those that effect altered ERF-VII levels with minimal impact on other PCO targets. Gene editing will enable incorporation of these variants into the Arabidopsis genome and, ultimately, findings in Arabidopsis can be translated into crop species in which PCO sequences are highly conserved (Gunawardana et al., 2021). The premise of this approach seeks to engineer endogenous enzymes to alter their catalytic properties and improve stress tolerance characteristics. It can also reveal additional insights into the molecular mechanisms of submergence tolerance across different plant species. Coupling this strategy with semi-rational directed evolution methods has the potential to accelerate identification of enzyme variants which generate a positive outcome *in planta*. Such an approach could also be readily applied to enzymes involved in a number of other plant stress tolerance or productivity pathways.

To date, techniques to improve stress tolerance in plants have broadly been based upon trait mapping and conventional breeding, a widely used method which seeks to identify genetic loci associated with beneficial traits and transfer them into agriculturally relevant cultivars. This was of course successful in breeding *SUB1A* into lowland rice varieties (Xu et al., 2006) and continues to play a major role in generating crop lines fit for the 21st century, particularly alongside highly efficient gene editing techniques (Bailey-Serres et al., 2019). Arguably, however, the pace of this approach by itself is not fast enough to meet the food security needs of the next 30 years, and complementary strategies are needed. Synthetic biology seeks to introduce orthogonal components and pathways into plants to drive systems which are otherwise inaccessible (Wurtzel et al., 2019). This exciting field is progressing rapidly with significant potential gains such as bypassing photorespiration in C3 plants (Roell et al., 2021). Engineering enzymes that are already endogenous to the plant could be a more straightforward approach to improving stress tolerance in some circumstances. Indeed, the gene encoding the Arabidopsis Trehalase enzyme has recently been edited such that the substrate binding site mimics that of an equivalent enzyme from the drought-tolerant *Selaginella lepidophylla*; this single modification conferred increased drought tolerance in the modified plants (Nuñez-Muñoz et al., 2021). We anticipate that engineering the PCOs will be another opportunity to improve stress tolerance and that coupling enzyme engineering with directed evolution offers an opportunity

to accelerate success in producing crops capable of withstanding current and future climates.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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